

APPLICATION OF PARALINGUISTIC MEANS

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Abstract. This article clarifies the types and features of paralinguistic tools in the language and typical paralinguistic means which are used by Uzbek people. Teaching foreign languages, it turned out that learning the language itself is not enough for a complete understanding of the native speakers of the language being studied due to the presence of paralinguistic phenomena that are caused by national or cultural specifics such as the manner in which one expresses emotions, gestures, and makes human contacts.

Key words: paralinguistics, facial expressions, tone, kinetic, mimic, shake, greeting.

“Paralinguistics” is derived from the Latin words para (adjacent), lingua (language), meaning “adjacent to the language”, “used in conjunction with the language” [2]. This term was first proposed by A. Hill. Treyger later wrote a work on the subject, defining its substance (the subject, the task, the nature of the events being studied, etc.). In the classroom paralinguistic features of language are extremely important as they can change message completely. Tone and pitch of voice is commonly dealt with at all language levels, but a fuller consideration of paralinguistics is often left to very advanced courses.

The results of the comparison of paralinguistic means show that for each nation there is a semiological reality of gestures and facial expressions, which differs in social and national-cultural characteristics, customs, rituals, traditions and religious habits. Therefore, it is impossible to transfer the symbolism of gestures adopted in the culture of one people into the culture of another, since in this case there can be no full-fledged communication or it becomes difficult [1].

Paralinguistic means in the Uzbek language can be learned according to these divisions:

- a) kinetic
- b) mimic
- c) phonetic .

1. The structure of the Uzbek language means denial, affirmation, demonstration, farewell, intimidation, greeting, as well as the use of various kinetic means to convey emotions in the process of opinion expression.

For example, the horizontal movement of the head means “no”. “Boshini chayqamoq” (Shake your head) is expressed by the verbal means. Kinetic devices are also common in Uzbek. The vertical movement of the head means “yes”. This condition is characterized by verbal means such as “bosh irg`idi”, “bosh silkitdi”, “boshini qimirlatdi” (nod your head). For example: *Zuhra kelin indamay bosh irg`adi (Zukhra nodded saying nothing)* [4].

2. Kinetic hand gestures are also used to express affirmation as a paralinguistic feature. In addition to auxiliary means of denial and affirmation, there are also paralinguistic means of representation (an object, thing, or event). Kinetic hand gestures are actively used to express the meaning of a show. In the text, this action is expressed by verbal means, such as “barmog`ini bigiz qildi”. For example: *Rais buva avvaliga bizni tanimadi shekilli, qo`lini paxsa qildi (At first, the chairman didn't seem to recognize us, so he shook his hand)* [5].

In conclusion, paralinguistic methods are an integral part of foreign language teaching. Paraphonetic means are included in the process of teaching pronunciation, and parakinesic means must be studied in intercultural and non-verbal communication. Such as Uzbek paralinguistic means are interesting and it is being learnt by linguists even nowadays.

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